

QUIZ

LAST NAME: JESO

FIRST NAME: MOHAMED

PROGRAM CODE: MBAIF

COURSE CODE : ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **A writer uses an information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is?**
 - The consideration of starting the body of the writing.
 - To avoid plagiarism in an academic writing.¹**
 - Sourcing from different irrelevant and distinctive.
 - To avoid reliable source from media journal.
2. **Which is an appropriate for an academic writing?**
 - Never use contractions such as “can’t”.²**

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Course pack* (Euclid University, Washington DC, 2015). <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/> (accessed January 23, 2020), 8.

² Ibid, 39.

- Never use the possessive form of "it".
 - Use of contractions and complete words together.
 - Avoiding abbreviations used in writing.
3. **The writer should think a logical and reasonable way in order to develop persuasive research papers, which of the following statements of academic paper is correct?**
- Unreasonable to persuade.
 - Avoiding fuzzy thinking.**³
 - Avoiding use of figures and diagrams.
 - Avoiding double checking of the paper.
4. **Which of the following words describe the common types of literature?**
- Parable, judge, emotion.
 - Allegory, biography, drama.**⁴
 - Exam, faculty, treaty.
 - Textbook, author, reporter.
5. **Which of the following statements is incorrect when incorporating quotations into your essay?**
- Do not put a comma after quotation.

³ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000*: (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 305.

⁴ Ibid, 356.

- If the quotation of citation is five lines or longer.**⁵
- If the quotation of citation is less five lines.
- Put a comma before the quotation.
6. **Which of the following statements is correct of Turabian style date systems format?**
- Month, day, and year.**⁶
- Year, month, day
- Day, month, year
- Month, year, day
7. **Which of the following statements pose a threat to document acceptance?**
- Inadequate proofreading and unnecessary background.**⁷
- A professionally written research paper.
- Careful and adequate drafted research paper.
- Grammatical rules and correct spelling.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (University of Chicago Press, 2013), 208.

⁶ Ibid, 193.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack*. (Euclid University, Washington DC, 2015) <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-4/> (accessed January 23, 2020), 4.

8. **There is many unsuitable references which is not required in research paper, which one of the following statements describe irrelevant information?**
- Referred background information source.
 - Anecdotal and considered as unnecessary.**⁸
 - Specification of the appropriate article.
 - Written statement of any communication.
9. **Which of the following statements is a procedural phrase that has similar expressions to "ex rel"?**
- For the use of, on behalf of, as next friend of.**⁹
 - In case of, for example, for information.
 - In lieu of, instead of, in spite of, despite of.
 - In expression of, for the period, in addition.
10. **Which of short form indicating to refer to the immediately preceding citation?**
- The use of ass'n, bros., coins.
 - The use of "id." or "supra."**¹⁰
 - The use of in re, or ex rel.
 - The use of ltd, L.L.C., N.A., F.S.B.

⁸ Ibid, 8.

⁹ The Bluebook: *A Uniform System of Citation* (Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review Association Cambridge, 2013), 112.

¹⁰ Ibid, 36.

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